

PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the residual strength of composite laminates with a notch using an effective crack growth model (ECGM). Damage is assumed to initiate when the local normal stress ahead of the notch tip reaches the tensile strength of the unnotched laminate. The damage was modelled by a fictitious crack with cohesive stress acting on the crack surfaces, and the damage growth was simulated by extension of the fictitious crack and reduction of the cohesive stress with crack opening. Based on the global equilibrium condition, an iterative technique was developed to evaluate the applied load required to produce the damage growth. The residual strength predicted from this new model correlated well with experimental data in the open literature for the different laminate configurations.

INTRODUCTION

Because of their importance in structure applications, composite laminates with through cut-outs have been the subject of considerable study. Criteria based on various physical assumptions have been used for residual strength prediction of notched laminates. A comprehensive review of current fracture models can be found in [1]. Based on the stress level at a characteristic distance ahead of a notch tip, Whitney and Nuismer [2,3] developed the well-known Point Stress Criterion (PSC) and Average Stress Criterion (ASC). However, the limitation of such approaches is that the characteristic distance is dependent on the subject laminate geometry and it has to be determined through fitting experimental residual strength data. In other words, such a procedure for predicting the notched strength is basically one of curve fitting, as addressed by Karlak [4]. The Damage Zone Criterion (DZC), a semi-empirical two-parameter model proposed by Eriksson and Aronsson [5], was based on the global equilibrium condition and the Dugdale stress distribution in the damage zone, which was simulated by a fictitious crack in the stress-intense region at the notch tip. The critical damage zone length was determined through fitting the experimental data, which was in line with a "characteristic distance".

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Generally speaking, the characteristics of failure mechanisms, such as stress redistribution, damage initiation and growth etc, are not involved in the previous "characteristic-distance" type models, which were normally developed to find out the stress state and/or corresponding damage at a given applied load. In the present study, a reverse route was applied, i.e to find the applied load corresponding to a given damage. Damage growth and stress redistribution are presented with increase of the applied load, and the residual strength of composite laminates was evaluated using an iterative technique.

THE EFFECTIVE CRACK GROWTH MODEL

Concerning a composite laminate with a through thickness cut-out, damage is assumed to initiate when the normal tensile stress at the notch tip reaches the unnotched laminate strength, σ_o . With increase of the applied load, the damage occurs, associated with stress-relaxation (Fig. 1). The degradation of the material within the damage region is simulated using a fictitious crack with cohesive stress σ_{coh} , acting on the crack surfaces as shown in Fig. 2. The parameter G_c^* is the apparent fracture energy [6], which is used to correlate the critical crack opening, v_c , and σ_o .

Figure 1. Schematics of damage in composite laminate, a) damage initiation, b) damage growth and stress relaxation.

The stress distribution, σ_y^* , ahead of the damage zone, as shown in Fig. 3, is described by a modified closed-form linear elastic stress distribution [5]. For the reason of equilibrium, σ_y^* is modified by $\Delta\sigma_y$

$$\sigma_y^* = \sigma_y + \Delta\sigma_y \tag{1}$$

where

$$\Delta\sigma_y = \sigma_o - \sigma_y \Big|_{x=a+c_i} \tag{2}$$

Figure 2. Fictitious crack and linear relationship between cohesive stress and crack opening.

Figure 3. Sketch of stress distribution along the net-section plane.

The applied load is in equilibrium with the resultant axial force acting on the net-section plane of the laminate. The equilibrium condition in the global approach can be expressed as [7]:

$$\sum_{n=1}^i F_{(n)} + \int_{a+c_i}^{W/2} (\sigma_y + \Delta\sigma_y) t dx = \sigma_{app}(i) \frac{W}{2} t \quad (3)$$

where t , W are the thickness and width of the specimen, respectively. Since the cohesive stress, σ_{coh} , depends on the crack opening profile, $v_{(n)}$, a $\sigma_{coh}-v_{(n)}$ relationship has to be established. The total crack opening profile can be described by

$$v_{(n)} = v_{\sigma_{coh}(n)} + v_{\sigma_{app}(n)} \quad (4)$$

It is obvious that the $v_{\sigma_{coh}(n)}$ (COD due to the cohesive stress) is of negative value to indicate crack closure under the cohesive stress.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF SPECIMENS WITH CENTRE CRACK

The residual strength of specimens with a centre crack can be obtained from Eq. (3) using the linear elastic stress distribution, σ_y , along the net-section plane (x - axis) for an infinite orthotropic plate:

$$\sigma_y = K_I \frac{x}{\sqrt{\pi a (x^2 - a^2)}} \quad (5)$$

The stress intensity factor, K_I , for a plate with a finite width can be described as:

$$K_I = \sigma_{app} Y\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (6)$$

where $Y(a/W)$ is the finite-width calibration function given by:

$$Y\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{W}{\pi a} \tan\left(\frac{\pi a}{W}\right)} \quad (7)$$

The total crack opening profile due to the applied load for the plane stress condition and the cohesive stress acting on crack surfaces was given in [7]. To account for the finite-width effect of specimens on the COD calculations, a finite width correction (FWC) factor should be applied. Following the procedure described in [8], an appropriate FWC was proposed [7]. Because the cohesive stress depends on the crack opening displacement, these equations, i.e Eqs. (3-5), cannot be solved simultaneously and an iterative approach has to be applied to find the actual values of $v_{(n)}$ and σ_{app} . The maximum value of the evaluated applied stress, σ_{app} , is the critical failure stress of the composite laminate, and the corresponding fictitious crack length is the critical damage zone length.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF SPECIMENS WITH HOLE

The residual strength of specimens with a centre hole can be obtained from Eq. (3) using the normal stress distribution, σ_y , [9]:

$$\sigma_y = \left\{ 2 + \left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) \left[5\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^6 - 7\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^8 \right] \right\} \frac{\sigma}{2} \quad (8a)$$

where

$$K_T^\infty = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{2}{A_{11}} \left(\sqrt{A_{11}A_{22}} - A_{12} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{2A_{66}} \right)} \quad (8b)$$

A_{ij} are the in-plane stiffness members. If the length of the fictitious crack, is much smaller than the hole diameter, the COD formulations for the edge cracks [10] are proposed to simulate the crack opening displacements of the fictitious crack:

$$v = \frac{4 \sigma \sqrt{c_{(i+1)}^2 - c_{(n-1)}^2}}{E_{11}} D \begin{pmatrix} c_{(n-1)} \\ c_{(i+1)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Using an iterative approach the applied load corresponding to the given damage growth was evaluated [11].

EVALUATION OF THE NEW MODEL

In this section the residual strengths of composite laminates containing a notch are evaluated using the effective crack growth model (ECGM). The predictions are compared with the experimental results and the evaluations from the previous models (the Point Stress Criterion (PSC) [2,3], and Damage Zone Criterion (DZC) [5]). Two group of experimental data for residual strength of notched T300/N5208 $[0/90]_{4S}$ (laminate A) [3] and T300/914C $[(\pm 45/0/90)_3/0/90/\pm 45]_S$ (laminate B) [12] were compared with the predictions.

For the reason of equilibrium, stress redistribution occurs with damage growth and increase of the applied load. This point has been taken into account in evaluating the applied load from the equilibrium condition at each step of the damage growth. The stress profiles along the fictitious crack and the undamaged ligament length are illustrated in Fig. 4 for laminates A ($W=25.1$, $2a=2.8$ mm). It can be clearly identified that the distribution of σ_y^* vary significantly for the steps from $i=2$ to 11 or 9, i.e. stress relaxation and redistribution occur with damage growth.

Figure 4. Redistribution of normal stress with damage growth.

PREDICTIONS OF RESIDUAL STRENGTH

To evaluate the residual strength of notched composite laminates from the other models, characteristic parameters have to be determined, i.e. a characteristic distance d_c for the PSC and a critical damage length d_i^* for the DZC. The calculated characteristic distances are: $d_c = 1.01$ mm, $d_i^* = 0.84$ mm for laminate A and $d_c = 0.97$ mm, $d_i^* = 1.2$ mm for laminate B. To evaluate the residual strength of notched composite laminates using the new model, the apparent fracture energy G_c^* should be determined. This value was estimated directly from the residual strength

data following the procedure described in [7]. The values of the apparent fracture energy are 56 KJ/m² and 29 KJ/m² for laminate A and B, respectively.

The effect of the crack length on the residual strength of the composite laminates with different notch/width ratios is illustrated in Fig. 5. For laminate A, the notch/width ratio of specimens changed between 0.1 and 0.3 or the crack size varied from 2.8 mm to 25.2 mm, the predictions from the new model are well in agreement with the experimental data.

Figure 5. Effect of crack size on residual strength.

The effect of the specimen width on the residual strength of the notched composite laminates with different width is illustrated in Fig. 6. It can be found that the residual strength raised clearly as the specimen width was increased, when the hole size was kept to be the same. The predictions from the new model agree very well with the experimental data.

Figure 6. Effect of specimen width on residual strength for D=10 mm.

CRITICAL DAMAGE ZONE LENGTH

When the applied load reaches the critical fracture load, the corresponding fictitious crack length can be referred to as the critical damage zone length. In Figure 7 the critical damage zone length is plotted versus the crack length for laminate A. It is of interest to see that the damage zone length evaluated by the ECGM is in the same order of magnitude of d_0 and d_1^* . However, it can be found that a longer crack length results in greater critical damage zone length. In other words the critical damage zone length is not a laminate constant and it is dependent on the specimen geometry.

Figure 7. Effect of specimen geometry on critical damage zone length.

CONCLUSIONS

The effective crack growth model (ECGM) has been applied to evaluate the tensile residual strength of composite laminates with notches. It was found that the predictions from the new model correlated very well with the experimental results from open literature. Stress redistribution and relaxation were identified with damage growth, which is well correlated with the failure mechanisms of notched composite laminates.

The major differences between the effective crack growth model and the previous residual strength models can be illustrated by two important characteristics, i.e stress redistribution and damage growth, which were not involved in most of the previous models. From the evaluation of the effective crack growth model, it has been found that for the composite laminates, a large notch size results in a greater critical damage zone size, i.e the critical damage zone size is not a laminate constant and it is dependent on specimen geometry.

It should be noted that in this study the values of the apparent fracture energy, G_c^* , for all laminates were determined directly from the residual strength tests. In fact G_c^* can also be determined from the standard coupon fracture tests [12].

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